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ABSTRACT

Recent ages have witnessed the way of leveraging cloud-based services for large scale easygoing storage, processing, and distribution. Security and privacy are among top concerns for the public cloud environments. Towards these security challenges, we propose and implement, on OpenStack Swift, a beautiful client-side deduplication schema for securely storing and sharing outsourced data by the agency of the public cloud. The idea of our proposal is two method. First, it ensures better confidentiality towards unauthorized users. That is, every client computes a using data key to encrypt the data that he intends to store in the cloud. As one, the data secure is managed by the data owner. Second, by integrating access rights in metadata file, an authorized user can decipher an encrypted file only with his private key.

KEYWORDS: Cloud Storage, Data Security, Deduplication, Confidentiality, Proof of Ownership.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the explosive growth of digital contents continues to rise the demand for new storage and network capacities, along with an increasing need for more cost-effective use of storage and network bandwidth for data transfer. As such, the use of remote storage systems is gaining an expanding interest, namely the cloud storage based services, since it provides cost-efficient architectures. These architectures support the transmission, storage in a multi-tenant environment, and intensive computation of outsourced data in a pay per use business model. For saving resources consumption in both network bandwidth and storage capacities, many cloud services, namely Dropbox, Wuala and Memopal, apply client side deduplication [10]. This concept avoids the storage of redundant data in cloud servers and reduces network bandwidth consumption associated to transmitting the same contents several times. Despite these significant advantages in saving resources, client data deduplication brings many security issues, considerably due to the multi-owner data possession challenges [10]. For instance, several attacks target either the bandwidth consumption or the confidentiality and the privacy of legitimate cloud users. For example, a user may check whether another user has already uploaded a file, by trying to outsource the same file to the cloud. Recently, to mitigate these concerns, many efforts have been proposed under different security models ([1], [4], [6]). These schemes are called Proof of Ownership systems (PoW). They allow the storage server check a user data ownership, based on a static and short value (e.g. hash value). These security protocols are designed to guarantee several requirements, namely lightweight of verification and computation efficiency. Even though existing PoW schemes have addressed various security properties, we still need a careful consideration of potential attacks such as Data Leakage and poison attacks, that target privacy preservation and data confidentiality disclosure. This paper introduces a new cryptographic method for secure Proof of Ownership (PoW), based on the joint use of convergent encryption and the Merkle-based Tree, for improving data security in cloud storage systems, providing dynamic sharing between users and ensuring efficient data deduplication[5].

Our idea consists in using the Merkle-based Tree over encrypted data, in order to derive a unique identifier of outsourced data. On one hand, this identifier serves to check the availability of the same data in remote cloud servers. On the other hand, it is used to ensure efficient access control in dynamic sharing scenarios.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

RELATED WORKS AND SECURITY ANALYSIS

The Proof of Ownership (PoW) is introduced by Halevi [8]. It is challenge-response protocol enabling a storage server to check whether a requesting entity is the data owner, based on a short value. That is, when a user wants to upload a data file (D) to the cloud, he first computes and sends a hash value $\text{hash} = H(D)$ to the storage server. This latter maintains a database of hash values of all received files, and looks up hash. If there is a match found, then D is already outsourced to cloud servers. As such, the cloud tags the cloud user as an owner of data with no need to upload the file to remote storage servers. If there is no match, then the user has to send the file data (D) to the cloud. This client side deduplication, referred to as hash-as-a-proof [16], presents several security challenges, mainly due to the trust of cloud users assumption. This Section presents a security analysis of existing PoW schemes.

A. Security Analysis

Despite the significant resource saving advantages, PoW schemes bring several security challenges that may lead to sensitive data.

- **Data confidentiality** – hash-as-a-proof schemes (e.g. Dropbox) introduce an important data confidentiality concern, mainly due to the static proof client side generation. For instance, if a malicious user has the short hash value of an outsourced data file, he could fool the storage server as an owner trying to upload the requested data file. Then, he gains access to data, by presenting the hash proof. As such, an efficient PoW scheme requires the use of unpredictable values of verifications.
- **Privacy violation** – sensitive data leakage is a critical challenge that has not been addressed by Halevi et al. in [2]. That is, cloud users should have an efficient way to ensure that remote servers are unable to access outsourced data or to build user profiles.
- **Poison attack** – when a data file D is encrypted on the client side, relying on a randomly chosen encryption key, the cloud server is unable to verify consistency between the uploaded file and the proof value hash. In fact, given a pair (hashD;Enck(D)), the storage server cannot verify, if there is an original data file D, that provides a hash value hash. As such, a malicious user can replace a valid enciphered file with a poisoned file. So, a subsequent user loses his original copy of file, while retrieving the poisoned version.

B. Related Works

In order to prevent private data leakage, Halevi et al. [2] proposed the concept of Proof of Ownership (PoW), while introducing three different constructions, in terms of security and performances. These schemes involve the server challenging the client to present valid sibling paths for a subset of a Merkle tree leaves [3]. The first scheme applies erasure coding on the content of the original file. This encoded version is the input for construction of the Merkle tree. The second purpose pre-possesses the data file with a universal hash function instead of erasure coding. The third construction is the most practical approach. Halevi et al. design an efficient hash family, under several security assumptions. Unfortunately,

the proof assumes that the data file is sampled from a particular type of distribution.

Recently, propose a PoW scheme over encrypted data. That is, the file is divided into fixed-size blocks, where each block has a unique commitment. The hash-tree proof is then built, using the data commitments. Hence, the owner has to prove the possession of a data chunk of a precise commitment, with no need to reveal any secret information. However, this scheme introduces a high computation cost, as requiring generation of all commitments, in every challenging proof request. In [1], the authors presented an efficient PoW scheme. They use the projection of the file into selected bit-position as a proof of ownership. The main disadvantage of this construction is the privacy violation against honest but curious storage server. In 2013, Jia et al. [6] address the confidentiality preservation concern in cross user client side deduplication of encrypted data files. They used the convergent encryption approach, for providing deduplication under a weak leakage model. Unfortunately, their paper does not support a malicious storage server adversary.

SYSTEM MODEL

The proposed system consists of the following modules:

1. System Initialization
2. User Registration
3. KDC setup

4. Attribute generation
5. Sign
6. Verify

Figure 1 illustrates a descriptive network architecture for cloud storage. It relies on the following entities for the good management of client data:

- *Cloud Service Provider (CSP)*: a CSP has significant resources to govern distributed cloud storage servers and to manage its database servers. It also provides virtual infrastructure to host application services. These services can be used by the client to manage his data stored in the cloud servers.
- *Client*: a client makes use of provider's resources to store, retrieve and share data with multiple users. A client can be either an individual or an enterprise.
- *Users*: the users are able to access the content stored in the cloud, depending on their access rights which are authorizations granted by the client, like the rights to read, write or re-store the modified data in the cloud. These access rights serve to specify several groups of users. Each group is characterized by an identifier IDG and a set of access rights.

In practice, the CSP provides a web interface for the client to store data into a set of cloud servers, which are running in a cooperated and distributed manner. In addition, the web interface is used by the users to retrieve, modify and restore data from the cloud, depending on their access rights. Moreover, the CSP relies on database servers to map client identities to their stored data identifiers and group identifiers.

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Figure:

Fig. 1: Architecture of cloud data storage

PROOF OF OWNERSHIP SCHEME

Our secure client-side data deduplication scheme is based on an original use of the convergent encryption [5]. That is, on one hand, when a data owner wants to store a new enciphered data file in remote storage servers, he has first to generate the enciphering key. This data encrypting key is derived by applying a one way hash function on data content. After successfully encrypting the file data, the client has to generate the data identifier of enciphered data, in order to check its uniqueness in cloud database, before uploading the claimed file. This data identifier is computed by

using a Merkle hash tree, over encrypted contents. Then, for subsequent data outsourcing, the client is not required to send the same encrypted data. However, he has to substitute a client-server interactive proof scheme (PoW), in order to prove his ownership. On the other hand, to protect data in public cloud servers from unauthorized entities, the client has to ensure that only authorized users are able to obtain the decrypting keys. As such, the data owner has to encrypt the data deciphering key, using the public key of the recipient user. This key is, then, integrated by the data owner in user metadata, ensuring data confidentiality against malicious users, as well as flexible access control policies. To illustrate our solution for improving data security and efficiency, we first present the different prerequisites and assumptions. Then, we introduce three use cases for storing, retrieving and sharing data among a group of users.

A. Assumptions

Our solution considers the following assumptions. First, we assume that there is an established secure channel between the client and the CSP. This secure channel supports mutual authentication and data confidentiality and integrity. Hence, after successfully authenticating with the CSP, these cloud users share the same resources in a multi-tenant environment. Second, our solution uses the hash functions in the generation of the enciphering data keys. Hence, we assume that these cryptographic functions are strongly collision resistant, as it is an intractable problem to find the same output for different data files.

B. Prerequisites

- *Merkle Hash Tree* – a Merkle tree MT provides a succinct commitment, called the root value of the Merkle tree, to a data file. That is, the file is divided into blocks, called tree leaves, grouped in pairs and hashed using a collision resistant hash function. The hash values are then grouped in pairs and the process is repeated until the construction of the root value. The Merkle tree proof protocol requires that the prover has the original data file. That is, the verifier chooses a number of leaf indexes and asks the verifier to provide the corresponding leaves. As such, the verifier has to send these leaves with a sibling valid path.
- *Interactive Proof System* – this proof system is an interactive game between two parties: a challenger and a verifier that interact in a common input, satisfying the correctness properties (i.e. completeness and soundness). In the following, we introduce our client-side deduplication construction, based on three different scenarios: storage, backup and sharing schemes.

C. Cloud Data Storage

When a client wants to store a new data file f in the cloud, he derives the enciphering key k_f from the data contents, based on a one-way hash function $H()$. Note that data are stored enciphered in cloud servers, based on a symmetric algorithm. Hence, the data owner has to encipher the data file that he intends to outsource. Then, he generates the data identifier MT_f . That is, it is the Merkle Tree over encrypted data. This identifier, associated to the file, must be unique in the CSP database. Thus, the client starts the storage process by sending a *ClientRequestVerif* message to verify the uniqueness of the generated MT_f to his CSP.

D. Cloud Data Backup

The data backup process starts when the client requests for retrieving the data previously stored in the cloud. The data backup process includes the following messages:

- *ClientRequestBackup*: it contains the URI of the requested data that the client wants to retrieve. Upon receiving this client request, the CSP verifies the client ownership of the claimed file and generates a *ResponseBackup* message.
- *ResponseBackup*: in his response, the CSP includes the encrypted outsourced data $k_f(f)$. Upon receiving the *ResponseBackup* message, the client first retrieve the file metadata and decipheres the data decrypting key k_f , using his secret key. Then, he uses the derived key to decrypt the request data file.

DATA DEDUPLICATION BASED SYSTEM

In order to evaluate the performances of our proposal, we build a simulated cloud storage framework, based on OpenStack Storage system (Swift). Swift is a cloud based storage system, which stores data and allows write, read, and delete operations on them. To achieve security enhancement of Swift, we extend its functionalities with algorithms and protocols designed in our scheme. We have designed our own architecture, performing an installation of swift.

Indeed, our architecture consists in dividing the machine drive into four physical volumes. Then, each volume is divided into four logical volumes. In total, we obtain sixteen partitions, each one represents one logical storage zone. The simulation consists of two components: the client side and the cloud side. We implement several cryptographic algorithms based on cryptographic functions from the OpenSSL library, the GMP library and the Pairing Based Cryptography (PBC) library, with independent native processes.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to evaluate the performances at the client side, we first conduct data encryption and decryption tests locally. Second, we evaluated the time consumption of random data upload in the cloud, or data download from remote servers. For our tests, we used 1000 samples in order to get our average durations.

- 1) *Client-Side Computation*: To evaluate client side computation costs, we conduct data symmetric encryption and decryption, using a symmetric cryptographic algorithm.
- 2) *Upload/Download* : In this section, we evaluated the time consumption of random data upload in the cloud, or data download from remote servers. Our approach consists at first, to generate a random data file of a fixed size. Then, we encrypt the data file based on the basis of algorithm. Afterwards, we upload the encrypted file and we download it from the cloud. As such, we conducted some tests by choosing different files of different sizes. At each time, we computed the average time for uploading and downloading the encrypted file. Next, we present the results of average time computation to upload and download data file in the cloud.

Finally, we conclude that the cryptographic operations, at the client side are acceptable compared to the upload operations and do not carry exhaustive computation capacities.

In summary, our performance evaluation presents the efficiency of our proposal in content processing and delivery. At the client side, our scheme brings acceptable computation costs. The overhead of the implemented security mechanisms does not affect the client resources. At the cloud side, our deduplication proposal preserves the efficiency of content upload/download operations with a smaller overhead of cryptographic operations.

CONCLUSION

Our solution is based on a cryptographic usage of symmetric encryption used for enciphering the data file and asymmetric encryption for meta data files, due to the highest sensibility of these information towards several intrusions. In addition, thanks to the Merkle tree properties, this proposal is shown to support data deduplication, as it employs an pre-verification of data existence, in cloud servers, which is useful for saving bandwidth. Besides, our solution is also shown to be resistant to unauthorized access to data and to any data disclosure during sharing process, providing two levels of access control verification. Finally, we believe that cloud data storage security is still full of challenges and of paramount importance, and many research problems remain to be identified.

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